

TEACHING GRAMMAR WITH “THE PASS THE POINTER” TECHNIQUE

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The purpose of this thesis is to show the effect of teaching grammar with new suitable method on acquiring English as a foreign language for young learners. The researcher used to sample process to conduct this study. The finding of this research indicated that there is a positive effect of teaching grammar with acceptable method, which teaching grammatical rules through games, on English as a foreign language acquisition by youthful learners. This research concluded that young learners, who were taught by using new method, progressed notably in learning grammar in which they got better knowledge. This study recommends that further future research be conducted in this method to overcome problems with second language acquisition especially in teaching grammar.

Grammar is an essential part of learning and teaching any foreign languages. There are many opinions within the language learning community on the part of teachers and learners regarding grammar. Some people believe that a grammar-based approach is key to efficiently learning a language. They claim that a thorough grammar study is necessary for understanding the structure of the language. They insist that without understanding grammar, a language would be a jumble of words difficult to decipher. Some go as far as to say that they first need to have a good grasp of grammar even before starting learning the language.

On the other hand, others believe exactly the opposite: that grammar books are an unnecessary obstacle that slow down the learning process. Teaching grammar is

an essential part of school education. Without grammar, spoken or written words lose much of their meaning and most of their value. Grammar rules should be exclusively inferred by the language and not vice-versa.

On teaching grammar to A1 level learners various teaching techniques might be used. One of the effective teaching techniques is considered to be "Pass the Pointer". This technique sometimes can be used not only in grammar lessons, but also in vocabulary lessons as well. The using procedure of this technique requires some electronic equipment because "the pointer" should be the light of laser and the electronic board is also needed in order to use this technique. However, in my own experience I simplified the usage of this technique regarding the facilities and the age of my learners and my main tools were pointer stick and the blackboard and vivid pictures. To be specific, "Pass the Pointer" technique is suitable for the grammar topics which may include some visual illustrations. For instance, on teaching the grammar topic "Prepositions" to A1 level pupils, the teacher prepares the visualized illustrations of the meanings of prepositions of place. In such case, in order to explain the meaning of preposition of "on" the teacher may choose the picture with an apple standing on the table. Then she sticks such pictures on the blackboard and points at them turn by turn. The pupils say out loud what they understand in each pointed picture and simultaneously try to analyze the meaning of the prepositions.

One another way to use the "Pass the pointer" might be silently used not whole class but with individual pupils. Specifically the teacher shows the cards to the pupil with a name of preposition inside and the pupil should take the pointer stick and show the illustrated meaning of that preposition.

It can be assumed that, the technique "Pass the Pointer" helps pupils both to absorb the meaning of grammar rules and memorize their illustration with the help of visual aids for a long term.

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